

INFLUENCE OF THE INTERFACE ON THE APPARENT FRACTURE TOUGHNESS AND CRACK PROPAGATION DIRECTION IN LAYERED CERAMIC COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

One of the material properties that limits the use of ceramic materials is their low resistance against crack propagation. A possible ways how to reach higher resistance against crack propagation in ceramic materials is e.g. layering of different ceramic materials. Crack propagates close to the interfaces between layers with different material properties in such kind of composite. The crack can be slowed down or absolutely stopped close to the interface due to specific properties of the ceramic laminate.

The increase in fracture toughness in laminate composite materials is documented in many publications. Specifically, ceramic-based composite $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2$ on which this contribution is focused, many papers were dedicated. For example, in publications [1-6] are described technological procedures of this ceramic composite and results of experimental measurement of the apparent fracture toughness. It is clearly documented that fracture toughness can be increased up to 200% - compared to the maximum value of the fracture toughness of the composite material with the values of individual components that make up the laminate.

The crack propagation in the layered ceramic composite exhibits "step-wise" character, see Figure 1 and e.g. [1-6] for details. The change of the direction of crack propagation after passing through the interface is caused by different material properties of the individual layers. However, the main reason for the crack propagation direction change and creation of "stairs" are strong residual stresses developed in the layers during sintering process. $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2$ laminate is produced by sintering at temperatures reaching 1500°C [1-3]. If such a composite is cooled to room temperature, due

to the different coefficients of thermal expansion of the individual layers high residual stresses are formed [1-6].

Fig. 1. Step-wise fracture of an alumina–zirconia based layered composite under flexural loading (with courtesy of Raúl Bermejo).

2 Numerical modeling

The behavior of the crack in the studied kind of laminate can be estimated with help of numerical modeling. Finite element method was used for modeling of the "step-wise" mechanism of crack propagation e.g. in [7-10]. The criteria based on generalized form of Sih's strain energy density factor (SED) [11] were used for an estimation of apparent fracture toughness of the layered composite body and change of the crack propagation direction close to the material interface.

To simplify the problem, all works mentioned above are limited to two-dimensional solution, thereby

neglecting the thickness of the composite and real stress distribution around the crack front. Nevertheless, for better description of the crack propagation in the composite it is desirable to include the third dimension in the solution, i.e. to reflect the real crack front shape during crack propagation.

The contribution is focused on the influence of laminate composition (material properties of components, number and thickness of layers, etc.) on the apparent fracture toughness of the layered ceramic composite and on the effect of the material interface and residual stresses on the change of the crack propagation direction close to the interface. The change of the crack propagation direction contributes to the better resistance of the composite to the crack propagation.

The crack behavior is described by procedures based on (generalized) linear elastic fracture mechanics. Special attention is devoted to the development of the crack in the first layer of the composite and its behavior on the interface. The real crack front shape during crack propagation is investigated in detail. For reliable estimation of the crack behavior the three dimensional FEM models were developed taking into account the real crack front shape during crack propagation. The calculations were performed for various components of the composite and different volume ratios.

The influence of the laminate composition on critical values for crack propagation through the material interfaces and on the apparent fracture toughness of the composite was determined.

The study contributes to the better understanding of damage of the layered composites.

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